

Neuronal density-DG
Performed by Rami
Date:08/13/2021

Two weeks post injury

Data File	Marker	Total Markers Counted	Number of Sections	Region	Number of Sampling Sites
TBI-Aged-VEH-NUMBER11.DAT	DG	3392	9	DG	295
TBI-Aged-VEH-NUMBER12.DAT	DG	2989	8	DG	281
TBI-Aged-VEH-NUMBER13.DAT	DG	3912	10	DG	316
TBI-Aged-VEH-NUMBER14.DAT	DG	2805	9	DG	293
TBI-Aged-VEH-NUMBER15.DAT	DG	4039	10	DG	239
TBI-Aged-VEH-NUMBER16.DAT	DG	2724	9	DG	207
TBI-Aged-VEH-NUMBER17.DAT	DG	2424	8	DG	232
TBI-Aged-VEH-NUMBER18.DAT	DG	2432	9	DG	196
TBI-Aged-PLX-NUMBER11.DAT	DG	4074	9	DG	328
TBI-Aged-PLX-NUMBER12.DAT	DG	4027	8	DG	250
TBI-Aged-PLX-NUMBER13.DAT	DG	3569	8	DG	305
TBI-Aged-PLX-NUMBER14.DAT	DG	3692	9	DG	326
TBI-Aged-PLX-NUMBER15.DAT	DG	3475	8	DG	302
TBI-Aged-PLX-NUMBER16.DAT	DG	2876	9	DG	179
TBI-Aged-PLX-NUMBER17.DAT	DG	4463	9	DG	226
TBI-Aged-PLX-NUMBER18.DAT	DG	5858	9	DG	310

Estimated Population using Mean Section Thickness	Counting Frame Area (XY) (μm^2)	Measured Volume (μm^3) [5]	Measured Volume (mm^3) [5]	Neuronal count per mm^3	Average-Neuronal count per mm^3
106632.21	900.0	116737000.0	0.116737	913440	
103189.61	900.0	127383000.0	0.127383	810074	
116222.23	900.0	134462000.0	0.134462	864350	
95285.61	900.0	116085000.0	0.116085	820826	
160767.44	900.0	151284000.0	0.151284	1062686	
104959.14	900.0	113794800.0	0.113795	922354	
104811.40	900.0	101091700.0	0.101092	1036795	
105034.71	900.0	104455400.0	0.104455	1005546	929509
133017.98	900.0	123609000.0	0.123609	1076119	
149485.14	900.0	115443400.0	0.115443	1294878	
135276.77	900.0	123408000.0	0.123408	1096175	
151457.50	900.0	127539000.0	0.127539	1187539	
132305.78	900.0	122178000.0	0.122178	1082894	
130106.91	900.0	136302800.0	0.136303	954543	
204527.30	900.0	150710100.0	0.15071	1357091	
232740.22	900.0	166807000.0	0.166807	1395267	1180563